

Heterometallic Lanthanide/Mercury Complexes of Sarcosine and L-Proline

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Reaction of mercury(II) acetate, hydrated $M(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (where $M = \text{La-Yb}$) with sarcosine or L-proline in methanol produces heterometallic complexes of stoichiometry $[(\text{HgL}_2)_2 M(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ (where L is the amino acid anion). Sarcosine also forms the compounds $[(\text{HgL}_2)_2 Y(\text{NO}_3)_3]$, $[(\text{HgL}_2)_2 \text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4]$, $[(\text{HgL}_2)_3 \text{Zn}_2(\text{NO}_3)_4]$. These compounds were characterised by spectroscopic methods, as crystals suitable for X-ray studies were not obtained.

Recently we have shown that lactam rings of general formula **1** and related ligands such as 2-oxazolidone (**2**) are very versatile in their ability to generate polymeric Hg/M heterometallic complexes with unusual structures, containing macrocyclic rings incorporating the metal atoms as part of the ring framework¹⁻³. The metallomacrocycles which result are of differing sizes. Variations in the nature of the metal ion, M, accompanying the mercury, and in the lactam ring size, result in a number of ways in which these rings link to form chains of rings, sheets of rings (sometimes with contiguous arrays of different ring sizes^{3,4}) or three-dimensional networks.

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In these complexes the lactam rings behave as ambidentate (N, O donor) ligands in which the O-donor atom is from a carbonyl group. In view of the facility with which such Hg/M complexes may be obtained, we were interested to see if similar

compounds could be formed by a somewhat related N, O donor ligand, the amino acid L-proline (=prol) (**3**) which, like 2-pyrrolidone and 2-oxazolidone, contains a five-membered ring. This has proved to be the case and we report here the results of this work, and on the related open chain amino acid sarcosine (=sar) (**4**).

Results and Discussion

The ligands L-proline and sarcosine each produced an extensive series of heterometallic Hg/M complexes with lanthanide nitrates in good yield (80–90%) by mixing mercury(II) acetate, the amino acid, and the appropriate metal salt in methanol (Tables 1 and 2). In our previous work with the lanthanide(III)/mercury(II) complexes with lactams and related ligands we observed two main stoichiometries— $[\text{MHg}_2\text{L}_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ and $[\text{M}_2\text{Hg}_3\text{L}_6(\text{NO}_3)_6]$ —and there is often a change in stoichiometry as one moves across the lanthanide series. With both L-proline and sarcosine the stoichiometry is $[\text{MHg}_2\text{L}_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ and this is retained right across the lanthanide series, as was found to be the case for the related complexes formed by 2-oxazolidone³. As has been observed with some related Hg/M lactam complexes and with complexes of 'extended reach' bis-lactam or bis-pyridone ligands^{5,6} there is a tendency for these complexes to retain solvent molecules; the proline complexes form monohydrates and the sarcosine complexes retain some solvate methanol when $M = \text{La-Eu}$.

Sarcosine also gave the complexes $[\text{ThHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_4]$ and $[\text{Zn}_2\text{Hg}_3(\text{sar})_6(\text{NO}_3)_4]$. The 2 : 3 Zn : Hg ratio in the zinc complex has been

observed before in the structurally characterised Zn/Hg complex formed by 2-pyrrolidone⁷. A pink Co/Hg complex and a blue Cu/Hg complex were also formed on reacting mercury(II) acetate, sarcosine and cobalt(II) nitrate, or copper(II) nitrate respectively, in methanol, but the products were very hygroscopic and could not be reliably characterised.

The complexes have been studied by relevant spectroscopic methods as attempts to obtain them in crystalline form suitable for full X-ray characterisation were unsuccessful; they were found to be insoluble in the usual organic solvents and they could not be recovered after dissolution in water.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND $\nu_{as}(\text{CO}_2)$ VALUES FOR THE COMPLEXES $[\text{MHg}_2(\text{prol})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (prol = L-PROLINE)

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu_{as}(\text{CO}_2)$ cm^{-1}
		C	H	N	
M = La	White	19.9 (20.0)	2.8 (2.8)	7.9 (8.2)	1 592
Ce	White	19.8 (20.0)	2.7 (2.8)	8.0 (8.2)	1 594
Pr	Pale green	19.9 (20.0)	2.7 (2.8)	7.7 (8.2)	1 598
Nd	Lilac	19.6 (19.9)	2.6 (2.8)	7.6 (8.1)	1 596
Sm	White	20.0 (19.8)	2.5 (2.8)	7.9 (8.1)	1 596
Eu	White	19.8 (19.8)	2.5 (2.8)	7.7 (8.1)	1 598
Gd	White	19.5 (19.7)	2.5 (2.8)	7.7 (8.0)	1 598
Tb	White	19.6 (19.7)	2.6 (2.8)	7.6 (8.0)	1 601
Dy	White	19.7 (19.6)	2.8 (2.8)	7.5 (8.0)	1 608
Ho	Pink	19.7 (19.6)	2.6 (2.8)	7.5 (8.1)	1 606
Er	Pink	19.6 (19.5)	2.6 (2.8)	7.7 (8.0)	1 610
Tm	White	19.5 (19.5)	2.6 (2.8)	7.7 (8.0)	1 610
Yb	White	19.5 (19.4)	2.5 (2.8)	7.7 (7.9)	1 611
Hg (prol) ₂	White	27.8 (27.8)	3.7 (3.7)	6.4 (6.5)	1 575

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA AND $\nu_{as}(\text{CO}_2)$ VALUES FOR SARCOSINE (=SAR) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			$\nu_{as}(\text{CO}_2)$ cm^{-1}
		C	H	N	
$[\text{YHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	14.1 (14.0)	2.5 (2.4)	9.4 (9.5)	1 602
$[\text{LaHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	White	13.8 (13.7)	2.3 (2.4)	8.7 (9.0)	1 587
$[\text{CeHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	White	13.8 (13.7)	2.3 (2.4)	8.7 (8.9)	1 594
$[\text{PrHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	Green	13.7 (13.7)	2.1 (2.4)	8.6 (8.9)	1 587
$[\text{NdHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	Lilac	13.6 (13.6)	2.2 (2.4)	8.6 (8.9)	1 588
$[\text{SmHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	White	13.6 (13.6)	2.2 (2.4)	8.6 (8.9)	1 596
$[\text{EuHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3] \cdot 0.5\text{MeOH}$	White	13.4 (13.6)	2.3 (2.4)	8.6 (8.9)	1 598
$[\text{GdHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	13.1 (13.1)	2.5 (2.2)	8.7 (8.9)	1 592
$[\text{TbHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	13.1 (13.1)	2.6 (2.2)	8.7 (8.9)	1 598
$[\text{DyHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	13.1 (13.1)	2.4 (2.2)	8.7 (8.9)	1 600
$[\text{HoHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	Pink	13.0 (13.0)	2.5 (2.2)	8.6 (8.9)	1 600
$[\text{ErHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	Pink	13.2 (13.0)	2.5 (2.2)	8.6 (8.9)	1 602
$[\text{TmHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	13.0 (13.0)	2.2 (2.2)	8.5 (8.9)	1 602
$[\text{YbHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$	White	13.0 (12.9)	2.2 (2.2)	8.4 (8.8)	1 598
$[\text{ThHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_4]$	White	11.2 (11.7)	1.9 (2.0)	8.7 (9.1)	1 626, 1 598
$[\text{Zn}_2\text{Hg}_3(\text{sar})_6(\text{NO}_3)_4]$	White	14.5 (14.3)	2.7 (2.6)	9.0 (9.3)	1 590

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (cm^{-1}) AND ASSIGNMENTS FOR THE SOLID COMPLEXES $[\text{MHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$, WHERE sar = SARCOSINE

M							
Pr	Ground term $^3\text{H}_4$						
$^3\text{F}_2$	5 180	$^3\text{F}_3$	6 540	$^3\text{F}_4$	6 900	$^1\text{G}_4$	9 800
$^1\text{D}_2$	16 980	$^3\text{P}_0$	20 750	$^3\text{P}_1$	21 370	$^1\text{I}_6$	22 220
$^3\text{P}_2$	22 730						
Nd							
	Ground term $^4\text{I}_{9/2}$						
$^4\text{I}_{15/2}$	5 970	$^4\text{F}_{3/2}$	11 500	$^2\text{H}_{9/2}$	12 630	$^4\text{F}_{7/2}$	13 480
$^4\text{S}_{3/2}$	13 570	$^4\text{F}_{9/2}$	14 750	$^2\text{H}_{11/2}$	16 030	$^4\text{G}_{5/2}$	17 390
$^2\text{G}_{7/2}$	17 480	$^4\text{G}_{9/2}$	19 600	$^2\text{G}_{9/2}$	21 140	$^4\text{G}_{11/2}$	21 600
$^2\text{P}_{1/2}$	23 360	$^4\text{D}_{3/2}$	28 250				
Sm							
	Ground term $^6\text{H}_{5/2}$						
$^6\text{H}_{13/2}$	5 160	$^6\text{F}_{1/2}$	6 330	$^6\text{H}_{15/2}$	} 6 600	$^6\text{F}_{5/2}$	7 090
				$^6\text{F}_{3/2}$			
$^6\text{F}_{7/2}$	8 100	$^6\text{F}_{9/2}$	9 260	$^6\text{F}_{11/2}$	10 340	$^4\text{F}_{3/2}$	18 220
$^4\text{G}_{7/2}$	20 120	$^4\text{I}_{9/2}$	20 580	$^4\text{M}_{15/2}$	20 700	$^4\text{I}_{11/2}$	21 370
$^4\text{I}_{13/2}$	21 650	$^4\text{M}_{17/2}$	22 320	$^4\text{M}_{19/2}$	23 640	$^6\text{P}_{5/2}$	} 23 920
						$^4\text{P}_{5/2}$	
$^4\text{L}_{13/2}$	24 570	$^4\text{P}_{7/2}$	26 390				
Tb							
	Ground term $^7\text{F}_6$						
$^7\text{F}_2$	5 000	$^7\text{F}_0$	5 810	$^5\text{G}_6$	26 530	$^5\text{L}_{10}$	27 100
$^5\text{G}_5$	27 800	$^5\text{D}_2$	28 010				
Dy							
	Ground term $^6\text{H}_{15/2}$						
$^6\text{H}_{11/2}$	5 880	$^6\text{H}_{9/2}$	} 7 720	$^6\text{F}_{9/2}$	9 170	$^6\text{F}_{7/2}$	11 240
		$^6\text{F}_{11/2}$			$^6\text{H}_{7/2}$		
$^6\text{F}_{5/2}$	12 820	$^4\text{F}_{9/2}$	20 920	<i>a</i>	25 700	<i>b</i>	27 400
$^6\text{P}_{5/2}$	27 510	$^6\text{P}_{7/2}$	28 490	$(^4\text{M}, ^4\text{I})_{15/2}$	28 690		
Ho							
	Ground term $^5\text{I}_8$						
$^5\text{I}_7$	5 130	$^5\text{I}_6$	8 550	$^5\text{I}_5$	11 240	$^5\text{F}_5$	15 550
$^5\text{S}_2$	18 450	$^5\text{F}_4$	18 590	$^5\text{F}_3$	20 620	$^5\text{F}_2$	21 190
$^3\text{K}_8$	21 410	$^5\text{F}_1$	22 220	$(^5\text{G}, ^3\text{G})_5$	24 040	$^5\text{G}_4$	25 900
$^3\text{K}_7$	26 180						
Er							
	Ground term $^4\text{I}_{15/2}$						
$^4\text{I}_{13/2}$	6 000	$^4\text{I}_{11/2}$	10 250	$^4\text{I}_{9/2}$	12 500	$^4\text{F}_{9/2}$	15 430
$^4\text{S}_{3/2}$	18 520	$(^2\text{H}, ^4\text{G})_{11/2}$	19 157	$^4\text{F}_{7/2}$	20 580	$^4\text{F}_{5/2}$	22 270
$^4\text{F}_{3/2}$	22 780	$(^2\text{G}, ^4\text{F})_{9/2}$	24 390	$^4\text{G}_{11/2}$	26 530	$^2\text{K}_{15/2}$	} 27 340
						$^2\text{G}_{9/2}$	
Tm							
	Ground term $^3\text{H}_6$						
$^3\text{F}_4$	5 840	$^3\text{H}_5$	8 230	$^3\text{H}_4$	12 900	$^3\text{F}_3$	14 660
$^3\text{F}_2$	15 200	$^1\text{G}_4$	21 370	$^1\text{D}_2$	27 780		
<i>a</i> $^4\text{F}_{7/2}$, $^4\text{I}_{13/2}$, $^4\text{M}_{21/2}$, $^4\text{K}_{17/2}$ lie close together in this region ¹¹ .							
<i>b</i> $^4\text{F}_{3/2}$, $^4\text{D}_{3/2}$, $^4\text{M}_{19/2}$ lie close together in this region ¹¹ .							

Infrared spectra : The ir spectra of L-proline and sarcosine in the solid state show only very weak bands in the normal N–H stretching region, but they

have absorption bands between 2 400 and 2 700 cm^{-1} , consistent with predominantly zwitterionic form⁸. They both exhibit two bands in the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO})_2$

region, at 1 563 and 1 626 cm^{-1} for L-proline and at 1 614 and 1 653 cm^{-1} for sarcosine.

Coordination of mercury(II) results in the disappearance of the absorption in the 2 400–2 700 cm^{-1} region. In the complex $\text{Hg}(\text{pro})_2$ there is a single, strong, sharp $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ band at 1 575 cm^{-1} , which in the heterometallic Hg/lanthanide complexes is slightly broadened and shifted to the range 1 592–1 611 cm^{-1} . These results are consistent with both Hg–N and Hg–O(carboxylate) bonding in $\text{Hg}(\text{pro})_2$ and the consequent formation of a polymer $[\text{Hg}(\text{pro})_2]_n$ (polymeric structures are well-established for HgL_2 complexes with related N, O donor ligands^{3,9}). In the absence of X-ray structural information one cannot say if the shift of $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ in the Hg/M heterometallic complexes reflects simultaneous binding of both Hg and the lanthanide ion to the carboxylate group or displacement of Hg–O bonding by the presence of the lanthanide ions. For the L-proline Hg/lanthanide complexes it is interesting to note that even allowing for some uncertainty in the precise band positions, there is a general gradation to higher $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ values as one traverses the lanthanide series (e.g. 1 592 cm^{-1} for the lanthanum complex, 1 611 cm^{-1} for the ytterbium complex) presumably reflecting the effects of the decrease in metal ion size.

Similar general behaviour was observed for the ir spectra of the heterometallic complexes formed by sarcosine, in that the $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ bands at 1 614 and 1 653 cm^{-1} for sarcosine were replaced by a single band at 1 587–1 602 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the metal complexes. An exception was the thorium complex $[\text{ThHg}_2(\text{sar})_4(\text{NO}_3)_4]$ which showed two $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CO}_2)$ bands (at 1 598 and 1 626 cm^{-1}).

Both series of complexes had nitrate bands at 824–831 cm^{-1} $\delta(\text{NO}_2)$ and ca. 1 040 $\nu_2(\text{NO}_2)$, but the complexity of the ir spectra in the 1 300–1 480 cm^{-1} region precluded sufficiently unambiguous identification of $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{CO}_2)$ ⁸ and the other expected¹⁰ N–O stretches.

Electronic spectra and epr measurements : The electronic spectra of both series of solid heterometallic Hg/lanthanide complexes were measured by the reflectance method. The results for the sarcosine complexes are listed in Table 3 together with proposed band assignments¹¹ (those

for the proline analogues are very similar). As expected, they parallel very closely those of the polymeric Hg/lanthanide compounds with pyridones¹², lactams¹³ and related ligands³.

Preliminary studies by Gresley¹⁴ show that the metal ion luminescence of the solid Eu, Tb and Dy complexes with proline is in each case much weaker than observed for the analogous Hg/M compounds with e.g. 2-oxazolidone³, presumably because of poorer energy harvesting and transfer by the amino acid ligands.

We have measured the epr spectra, at X- and Q-band frequencies, of Gd^{III}-doped polycrystalline samples of $[\text{MHg}_2\text{L}_4(\text{NO}_3)_3]$ (M = Er, Nd; L = prol, sar) (nominal 1 mol% Gd doping) for comparison with the results obtained previously with the gadolinium-doped samples of the Hg/M complexes formed by 2-pyrrolidone¹⁵ and some related ligands^{3,16}. At Q-band frequency, both of the sarcosine compounds exhibit a strong, sharp band at ca. 1 217 mT ($g_{\text{eff}} = 2$), with some weaker, additional bands arising from the effects of zero-field splitting¹⁵. Unfortunately, these last were insufficiently resolved to permit reliable evaluation of the zero-field splitting parameters. The spectra also showed a weak band at 618 mT due to a forbidden ($\Delta M_2 = \pm 2$) transition. The spectra obtained at X-band frequency also exhibited strong, allowed transitions at ca. 337 mT and forbidden transitions at low field. Essentially similar results were given by the Gd-doped proline complexes.

In conclusion, this work shows that sarcosine and L-proline can, under appropriate conditions, simultaneously bind combinations of metal ions with quite different 'hard/soft' acidities, and it seems likely that a wider range of amino acids would form analogous complexes.

Experimental

Preparation of compounds : The standard method employed was the addition of a methanolic solution of the amino acid (L-proline or sarcosine) (0.2 mmol) to one of a hydrated metal nitrate (0.05 mmol). This was followed by the dropwise addition of a methanolic solution of mercury(II) acetate (0.1 mmol) to the stirred solution. A total of 10 cm^3 methanol was used for each preparation. Precipitation of the corresponding complexes commenced immediately. These were filtered off, washed with cold methanol and dried.

The complexes obtained and their analytical data (Microanalytical Laboratory, Imperial College) are listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Infra-red spectra were recorded on a 1720 Perkin-Elmer Fourier Transform spectrometer as nujol mulls in either KBr or CsI plates in the range 220–4 000 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were obtained by the reflectance method using a Beckman DK2 spectrometer on powder samples. Epr spectra were measured at room temperature on polycrystalline samples, using a Varian E12 X-band spectrometer and a Q-band spectrometer comprising a Varian 36GHz microwave bridge and a Newport 12-in type F magnet powdered by a C905 rotary generator and post stabiliser.

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